

MEDICAL SCIENCES

HISTOMORPHOLOGICAL EVALUATION OF VENOUS VESSELS IN THE SPINAL GANGLIA. ANIMAL MODEL OF STUDY

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Abstract

We present the morphological (histological and ultrastructural) peculiarities of venous vessels of spinal ganglia, especially the specific properties of extracapsular vessels under light and electron microscopic study. The research performed on male rat's spinal ganglia. The object of research fixated by intravascular perfusion, then embedded in Epon - Araldite blocks according to general methods accepted in microscopy. Also, from spinal ganglia taken after intra aortal administration of ink solution dissolved in 10% gelatin, prepared blocks. Obtained semithin and total cryostat section investigated under microscopes. The current study demonstrates cellular structure of venous vessels walls, source, formation and direction of venous vessels of spinal ganglia.

Keyword: spinal ganglia, postcapillary venule, collecting venule, ultrastructure

Introduction. One of the important conditions for a detailed morphofunctional study of the blood supply of organs and organ systems is to learn the composition and structural characteristics of the vessels involved in the organization of local blood circulation. From this point of view, investigation of the structure of the microcirculatory system vessels of the spinal ganglion, as well as the cellular and non-cellular elements composing their wall is particular important, because of it closely involved in the formation of neuropathies of various origins.

Taking into account that we have already published information about arterial vessels participated in vascularization of spinal ganglia [1, 2], the presented data will be devoted to the histotopography of internal venous vessels, types of formation and structure of their walls. We should first note that although the diameters of the venous vessels within the spinal ganglia are sometimes reaches to the 55 μm , but considering that their walls are composed of only one layer of endothelial cells and incomplete pericyte, they are not veins [3]. We will call it venules.

Aim of research were to study the morphological peculiarities (histological and ultrastructural composition) of venous vessels walls, source, formation and direction it within spinal ganglia.

Material and methods. The object of research is spinal ganglia (lumbar and thoracic) taken from 20 white rats, weighing 180-200 gr, bred under special patogen free conditions. Under ketamine/xylazine (100/10mg/kg) anesthesia, the thoracic cavity of rats was opened through parasternal incisions and injected into the ascending aorta through a catheter 2.5% glutaraldehyde solution prepared in 0.1M phosphate buffer (pH=7.4). Epon-Araldite blocks were prepared from the ganglia of 10 white rats after fixation by intravascular perfusion during 20-25 minutes. Obtained the semithin sections (1-2 μm) from the blocks on LKB-III ultratome were stained with methylene blue, azure II and basic fuchsin, respectively [4, 5].

The ink solution dissolved in 10% gelatin was injected into the ascending aorta of another 10 white rats with the same catheter (used for intravascular perfusion) until it outflow from the vena cava inferior, then the spinal ganglia was taken together with the spinal roots and nerves, fixed in 10% formalin solution, and frozen in a cryostat. Obtained the total sections with thickness of 100-150 μm were analyzed under light microscope. Both semithin and total sections were viewed under a Latimet (Leitz) microscope and pictures of the necessary parts were taken with a Pixera digital camera system.

Results. The semithin section of the spinal ganglion shown in Figure 1A. The center of slide occupied by the spinal ganglia itself, the posterior root entering the ganglion shown on the lower right, the anterior root resting on the top of ganglion, and the

forming spinal nerve seen clearly on the left, as well as the branches (ventral and dorsal) that depart from the latter and surrounding them the connective tissue sheaths with neurovascular elements.

Figure 1. Histotopography of spinal ganglion's vessels surrounding organ and intraorganic location (A), microscopic images of branching and formation of intraorganic vessels (B). The explanation is given in the text. Stain: methylene blue (A), cryostat sections of intravenously injected preparations that viewed by inversion methods on photoshop program (B). Scale bars: A 200μm, B 50μm.

The obtained materials show that while around the spinal ganglia within surrounding connective tissue elements located the arterial and venous vessels of different diameters (Fig. 1A), only arterioles, precapillary arterioles, capillaries, postcapillary and collecting venules, which are components of the microcirculatory system, are found inside the ganglion. In particular, it should be noted that along with main arteries and veins, lymphatic vessels included in microcirculatory system are not detected within spinal ganglia.

In the demonstrated histological slide attract attention the following facts:

- Clearly seen the histotopographical conditions of the vessels placed inside and around the spinal ganglia in semithin sections revealed after fixation by the intravascular perfusion method (Fig. 1A), as well as the cellular elements composing their walls (unstained areas against the background of darkly colored peripheral field) at higher magnifications of the light microscope (Fig. 1B)

- the density of the vessels located in the spinal ganglia, that is, the degree of blood supply, a noticeable increase in comparison with the ventral and dorsal roots, the spinal nerve and its branches, and the connective tissue elements located around the ganglion;
- none of the sheaths that directly covered all the named structures (connective tissue elements of spinal ganglia, ventral and dorsal roots, spinal nerve) have a special vascular network;
- the presence of arterioles and venous vessels with diameters above $100\mu\text{m}$, only in the connective tissue elements around the ganglion.

Based on the actual data presented, it can be said with complete certainty that the vessels involved in the

vascularization of spinal ganglia should be divided into only two groups - extraorganic and intraorganic [1, 2].

Comparison of obtained reports with literature data shows that [6] the density of spinal ganglia vessels in dogs is less than peripheral nerves. However, contrary to this, the data obtained in the present study and researches conducted in different species of animals, with the help of different methods [3, 7, 8] shown that, among the structures included to the peripheral nervous system, the density of vascular elements in the spinal ganglia is comparable to that of the cerebral cortex.

Figure 2. Microscopic images of vessels situated within spinal ganglia. Semithin section. Stain: A methylene blue and basic fuchsin, B and C methylene blue. The explanation is given in the text. Scale bars: A $50\mu\text{m}$, B and C $20\mu\text{m}$.

Most of the vessels starting from the precapillary arterioles, whose diameter varies between $4\text{-}10\mu\text{m}$, can be attributed to capillaries. However, the lumen of both the capillaries and the postcapillary venules (formed as a result of fusion capillaries) along its course alternated between the expanded and narrowed parts.

For example, the diameter of the capillary (indicated by the arrow in Fig. 1B) starting from the upper right side and to left, is $4\mu\text{m}$, $12\mu\text{m}$, $4\mu\text{m}$, $6\mu\text{m}$, $5\mu\text{m}$, $12\mu\text{m}$, and the diameter of the initial part of the

postcapillary venule formed by the combination of the capillaries located around it is $13\mu\text{m}$, while its diameter is only $6.5\mu\text{m}$ in the last part marked by the arrow. Postcapillary venules starting from the capillary network by different ways (Fig. 1B lower part), with diameters ranging from $11\mu\text{m}$ to $15\mu\text{m}$, by joining with each other in the subcapsular area of spinal ganglia and formed collecting venules with diameters equal to $30\text{-}55\mu\text{m}$. The latter flow to the extraorganic venous vessels by piercing the capsule of the spinal ganglia

Figure 3. Microscopic picture of intracapsular collecting venules in the subcapsular area (A), in the regions where penetrate the capsule (B, C). Semithin section. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: ICV- intracapsular venule, EpiV – epineurial venule, VR – ventral root. Stain: A, B methylene blue, C methylene blue / azure II + basic fuchsin. Scale bar: A, B 50 μm, C 100 μm.

The morphometric measurements performed on semithin sections of ganglions vessels fixed by the perfusion method and the composition of cells in the walls of the vessels show that the vast majority of vessels located inside the spinal ganglia belong to

venular vessels. For example, in the semithin section on Figure 2A demonstrated 12 of the 18 microvessels; in Figure 2B 4 of 7 vessels; In Figure 2C 4 out of 5 vessels are postcapillary and collecting venules revealed according to the diameter of their lumen.

Figure 4. Microscopic images of serial semithin sections of intracapsular collecting venules where they open into extracapsular venous sinuses. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: EpiV – epineurial venule, EndV – endoneurial venule. Stain: methylene blue. Scale bar 200μm in all three slide.

A cross-sections of pericytes and sometimes primitive muscle cells can be found in the area of contractions along the course of venules (Fig. 2B is indicated by an arrow). It should be noted that

sometimes the described contractions are also revealed in the areas where the capillaries pass into the postcapillary venule.

Figure 5. Microscopic images of mutual relation of intracapsular and extracapsular venous vessels of the spinal ganglion. A, B, C the cryostat sections revealed after intravascular perfusion-fixed and administered into the ascending aorta ink solution (dissolved in 10% gelatin). Microscopic image of a perfusion-fixed semi-thin section. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: ICV -intracapsular venule, EpiV – epineurial venule, EndV – endoneurial venule. Stain: methylene blue. Scale bars: A, B 100 μ m, C 200 μ m, C 50 μ m.

In the semithin section shown in Figure 2C is clearly visible at the junction of capillary with diameter 9 μ m into the postcapillary venule in 14 μ m diameter the cross-section of a pericyte (indicated by an arrow). While the enlarged parts of capillaries and venules serve to increase the exchange surface areas of microvessels, the location of cells with the ability constrictions around the narrow regions suggests that they participate in the regulation of intraganglionic blood flow.

The study of the used methods and sections (total, histological, semi- and ultrathin) clearly shows that most of the venous vessels included in the external vascular network of spinal ganglia take their origin from the intracapsular vascular network.

More clearly, the venous vessels formed as a result of the connections of the postcapillary venules in the endoneurial area of the spinal ganglia (Fig. 3, 4, 5) pierce the ganglion capsule and enter the external vascular network of the capsule.

On Figure 3A shown the collecting venule with a diameter of 23 μ m surrounded by a single layer of

endothelial cell placed in subcapsular area, which appears to be formed by the fusion of thin postcapillary venules and directed towards the capsule of spinal ganglia.

In Figure 3B, it is clearly seen that a venous vessel with a diameter of 58 μ m pierces the perineural cell layer of the capsule of spinal ganglia and enters between the bundles of collagen fibers of the epineurial layer.

In Figure 3C, a collecting venule with a diameter of 41 μ m in the endoneurial area can be seen completely piercing the capsular elements and enter the extracapsular area.

Among the connections between the intracapsular and extracapsular vascular networks with the presence of venous vessels, attract the interest on serial semithin sections is shown in Figure 4. In Figure 4A, in the epineurial layer of the capsule of spinal ganglia visible lumen with diameter of 84,93 μ m in the initial part of the photomicrograph (from left to right), and it continues as 99,84 μ m; 155,8 μ m; 178,72 μ m; 200,26 μ m; 287,64 μ m; 308,66 μ m; 333,71 μ m; 367,14 μ m, and at the end (in the lower left pole of the

image) observed a venous sinus with diameter of 404,51µm, similar to the sinuses of the dura of the brain.

The similarity with the venous sinuses is that despite their wide diameter, around the endothelial cells in their walls are located only bundles of collagen fibers

belonging to the epineural layer. In Figure 4A from the above described venous sinus separated the venous vessel (shown by an arrow) in diameter 55µm that lined by own endothelial cells and leaving the endoneurial area. In Figure 4B is observed the depicted endoneurial venule opened into the sinus (indicated by the arrow).

Figure 6. Microscopic (A) and ultrastructural (B, C) picture of extracapsular venous vessels of spinal ganglion. A semithin section, B, C electron micrographs. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: LECV – lumen of extracapsular vein, C-capsule of spinal ganglia, EpiV – epineurial venule, E1 and E2 – endothelial cells, P-pericyte, BCF -bundle of collagen fibers. Stain: A methylene blue, B uranyl acetate and pure lead citrate. Scale bars: A 20µm, B, C 500 nm.

It should be noted that in Figure 4A and 4B to the left of the venule indicated by arrow is the leg-like extension of the venous sinus (indicated by asterisks). In demonstrated the serial semithin section on Figure 4C, there is no doubt that the venule leaving the endoneurial area opens into the wide leg-like region of the venous sinus. Thus, the venous vessels leaving the endoneurial area of the spinal ganglia either do so alone

(Fig. 3), or alternately join the venous sinuses located within the capsule of the organ (Fig. 4).

On Figure 5A, 5B, 5C are shown the venous vessels originating from the intracapsular vascular network by different ways and their participation in the formation of the extracapsular vascular network. However, in Figure 5D are shown the sections of venous vessels that have completely left the capsule of

spinal ganglia and separated from it by loose connective tissue elements.

What is interesting is that while in the wall of the venous vessel with an average diameter of 45µm (on the left) participated only endothelial cells and located around them the collagen fibers, the thickening due to the placement of other cells in the wall of the venous vessel with an average diameter of 180µm (on the right) attracts attention (see below).

In Figure 6 demonstrated the electron microscopic images of a part of the extracapsular perisitic venule with an average diameter of 115µm and cellular, fibrillar structures involved in the organization of its wall. This vessels separated from the capsule of spinal ganglia by loose connective tissue elements.

Belonging to pericytic venules of the discussed type of vessel is determined by the following signs:

- whether at the light (Fig. 6A) or electron microscopic levels (Fig. 6B), the central parts of the endothelial cells, where the nucleus is located, are not bulging towards the vascular lumen compared to the arteries;

- non-detection of structures belonging to the internal elastic membrane or its fragments in the subendothelial area;

- placement of bundles of collagen fibers between the inner endothelial layer and the middle pericytic layer (indicated by a star in Fig. 7A);

- detection of vacuolo-vesicular clusters, which play a key role in the formation of transendothelial channels in the peripheral parts of endothelial cells (indicated by arrows in Fig. 7 A, B and C);

Figure 7. Electron microscopic images of the structures involved in the organization of the walls of extracapsular pericytic (A, B, C) and muscular (D) venules of spinal ganglion. The explanation is given in the text. Abbreviation: EpiV – epineurial venule, SMC-smooth muscle cells. Stain: uranyl acetate and pure lead citrate. Scale bars in all slides 500 nm

- in the periendothelial layer, located pericytes that the nucleus-cytoplasm ratio is low, the cytoplasm is light compared to muscle cells (Fig. 6C, Fig. 7A), and also in the perinuclear areas are rarely found mainly mitochondria, granular endoplasmic reticulum, ribosomes, Golgi complexes (Fig. 7B), dense bodies associated with their plasmalemma;

- In the electrograms shown in Figure 7C, 7D, the presence of caveolae (indicated by arrows in both pictures) associated with the plasmalemmas on the peripheral parts of the cells located in the periendothelial area, the dark cytoplasm due to the structures included in the actin-myosin complex can give the impression that they belong to muscle fibers.

However, the dense bodies associated with their plasmalemma are difficult to detect, their peripheral parts are thin, etc. indicates that the depicted cells belong to primitive muscle cells, which are considered to be a transitional form between pericytes and smooth muscle cells. The presence of vacuole-vesicular clusters in the endothelial layers (marked with an arrow in Fig. 7D) of the vessels, the excess area of surfaces of neighboring endotheliocytes resting on each other (Fig. 7D), etc. indicating that they also belong to pericytic venules.

Conclusion. Location of the veins in the subcapsular area and piercing the ganglion capsule on diagonally, by increasing or decreasing the postcapillary resistance due to the influence of the intraganglionic pressure, ensures the maintenance of the internal hydrostatic pressure at the proper level.

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